

A thermal sublimation generator of ^{131m}Xe

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Abstract: Stable and unstable isotopes of the heavy noble gas xenon find use in various medical applications. However, apart from ^{133}Xe , used for Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography, radioactive isotopes of xenon are currently complicated to obtain in small quantities due to the cost and availability. With the GAMMA-MRI project (<https://gamma-mri.eu>) in mind, we investigated a thermal sublimation generator of the long-lived excited state (isomer) ^{131m}Xe . This production method utilized the decay of ^{131}I in Na^{131}I powder, obtained commercially from a hospital supplier. Heating the Na^{131}I powder and cryogenic trapping of released ^{131m}Xe allowed to collect up to 88% of the produced xenon. Our method provides an isomeric mixture of ^{131m}Xe and ^{131}Xe . With improvements in scalability and chemical purification, this method could be a cost-effective source of ^{131m}Xe for small scale experiments.

Keywords: xenon production; ^{131m}Xe ; ^{131}I decay;

1. Introduction

Stable and radioactive isotopes of xenon are used in large quantities in medical imaging and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) applications. Xenon has several important qualities. First, it is inert, and doesn't interact chemically with the research subject, or sample. Second, the amplitude of the NMR signal acquired from xenon can be increased by several orders of magnitude if xenon is hyperpolarized by colliding it with optically pumped alkali atoms using the technique of Spin Exchange Optical Pumping (SEOP) [1]. In addition, xenon passively crosses the blood brain barrier, and can serve as a contrast agent to image the uptake of the inhaled gas into brain tissue. This can be used effectively for stroke diagnosis for instance [2]. The most widely used stable isotopes of xenon are the nuclear ground states of ^{129}Xe and ^{131}Xe . They are typically used in NMR studies of materials, and for Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) of the lungs [3–6]. Unstable ^{133}Xe is used in Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) for the diagnosis of pulmonary diseases [7,8]. The physical half-life of ^{133}Xe of 5.3 d makes it easy for radiopharmaceutical suppliers to manufacture and deliver it [8].

In the GAMMA-MRI project (<https://gamma-mri.eu>), we aim at developing a new imaging technique based on the MRI response from polarized unstable, SPECT-compatible nuclei. Our first test cases are radioactive xenon isomers, in particular the long-lived ^{129m}Xe , ^{131m}Xe , and ^{133m}Xe isomers. Optimising SEOP polarization of these isomers is one of the key components of the GAMMA-MRI project. For this purpose, it is advantageous to use the isomer which has the longest half-life and can be produced in an affordable way.

Here, we explore a generator of ^{131m}Xe ($t_{1/2} = 11.84$ d), via decay of a ^{131}I source obtained commercially from a hospital supplier. ^{131}I , like ^{133}Xe in its ground state, is in

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high-demand by hospitals and can thus be procured from radiopharmaceutical companies. They can be both produced from ^{235}U fission, upon ^{235}U irradiation with neutrons in nuclear reactor facilities: $^{235}\text{U}(n, f)^{133}\text{Xe}$ and $^{235}\text{U}(n, f)^{131}\text{I}$. To isolate and collect these isotopes, the ^{235}U target is dissolved, and the solution is separated into cells containing specific chemically-active elements [9]. This approach offers several benefits: a flexible delivery schedule (medical ^{131}I is available > 350 d/yr), established supply routes (to hospitals), and a relatively low cost for samples at the delivery point.

$^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ generators based on ^{131}I have been investigated before. For instance, [10] used a palladium metal surface to adsorb ^{131}I from a solution. That generator was then connected to vacuum tight setup placed vertically: with generator atop and a set of glass spheres underneath. Produced $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ was collected in the bottom-most glass sphere with liquefied air and the sphere was separated by sealing it off with a flame torch. In [11], a $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ generator is described, where a ^{131}I solution was precipitated on a fibreglass filter as palladium(II) iodide PdI_2 , inside a commercially available syringe filter. The syringe was connected to a carrier gas which, after the desired quantity of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ was produced, would sweep the $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ from the syringe filter and into another apparatus for a γ -ray spectroscopy. Both of these generators reported near unity $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ production efficiency. In a more recent publication [12], the production of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ from ^{131}I is mentioned but no details are given. To the best of our knowledge, $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ production from Na^{131}I powder has not been reported yet. In this manuscript, we fill this gap and report on $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ production from a Na^{131}I powder. Solid state sample is preferred for the GAMMA-MRI project, because it should introduce less water into the SEOP cell than a Na^{131}I solution. It is important for successful polarization to eliminate all sources of water that could oxidize rubidium used in the SEOP process. The objective of the present work was thus to establish the most suitable conditions to extract $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ from a Na^{131}I salt, and to optimise the collection efficiency.

2. Materials and Methods

Production of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ from ^{131}I decay involved the following procedure: (i) procurement of the ^{131}I source in the form of powder encapsulated in a gelatin shell, (ii) γ -ray spectroscopy of the ^{131}I source upon arrival at CERN, (iii) ^{131}I powder transfer from its gelatin shell in a quartz tube and γ -ray spectroscopy of both constituents, (iv) placement of the powder in the experimental installation for decay, (v) collection of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ from the ^{131}I powder at ambient temperature, or after heating, and finally (vi) $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ γ -ray spectroscopy. Three 50 MBq Na^{131}I samples were purchased and underwent the above steps.

2.1. Characteristics of the parent source

The parent nucleus for the $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ generator is ^{131}I whose following characteristics were considered: the half-life and branching ratio for the transition to $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$, the isotopic and chemical purity of ^{131}I , the state of ^{131}I (solid or liquid), its availability, the associated radiological risks, and finally the cost of the ^{131}I source and of its delivery.

^{131}I ($t_{1/2} = 8.02$ d) is a beta-gamma (β^- , γ) ray emitter, which decays to the isomer $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ ($t_{1/2} = 11.84$ d), and to the ground state ^{131}Xe (stable). The β^- transition that directly feeds $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ (level $11/2^-$) has the endpoint energy of 807 keV and occurs with a probability of 0.39(9)% [13]. There are also two other paths which indirectly feed $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ via the $9/2^-$ and $7/2^-$ levels. The $9/2^-$ path adds a probability of 0.333(5)% and the $7/2^-$ path 0.363(4)% [13]. The total population per ^{131}I decay calculated from mentioned values is 1.09(9)%. The amount of collected $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ nuclei is, thus, the result of two competing processes, a source term from the decay of ^{131}I , and a sink term due to $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ decay. The mathematical model describing isotopes in the decay chain ($^{131}\text{I} > ^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe} > ^{131}\text{Xe}$) as a function of time is Bateman's equation [14], which for ^{131}I gives:

$$N_{\text{mXe}} = B_{\text{I} \rightarrow \text{mXe}} N_{\text{I}0} \frac{\lambda_{\text{I}}}{\lambda_{\text{mXe}} - \lambda_{\text{I}}} (e^{-\lambda_{\text{I}} t} - e^{-\lambda_{\text{mXe}} t}), \quad (1)$$

with N_{I_0} the number of ^{131}I nuclei at t_0 , decaying into $N_{m\text{Xe}}$ ^{131m}Xe nuclei at the rate λ_I over a period t and with the branching ratio $B_{I \rightarrow m\text{Xe}}$. Additionally, ^{131m}Xe decays into stable ^{131}Xe at the rate $\lambda_{m\text{Xe}}$ in time t .

Figure 1. Calculated ^{131m}Xe activity (red) vs time. A source of ^{131}I (black) decays into ^{131m}Xe (red), which itself decays into ^{131}Xe (stable, not shown). This leads to a maximum activity plateau for ^{131m}Xe at around day 14.

Figure 1 presents the activity vs. time of 1 MBq (at $t_0 = 0$ d) of ^{131}I (black), and that of ^{131m}Xe (in red) in kBq. The maximum ^{131m}Xe activity is 3.23(1) kBq. It can be collected, at $t = 14$ d, and it corresponds to 0.324(1)% of the initial activity of the ^{131}I source placed in the experimental setup.

We identified a supplier of ^{131}I (Curium Pharma, Paris, France), which could regularly deliver this source at high radionuclidic purity (see subsection 2.2).

2.2. ^{131}I source manufacturing

Radiopharmaceutical preparation standards are defined in European Pharmacopoeia [15], and implemented by all manufacturers in Europe. They define the quality of ^{131}I medication, including the chemical and radionuclidic purity, and define accepted physical forms and dosage. The radionuclidic purity of ^{131}I is $\geq 99.9\%$ with ^{133}I , ^{135}I and other impurities $\leq 0.01\%$.

The ^{131}I bulk solution is delivered on a regular basis to our supplier Curium Pharma by the processors of reactor-irradiated targets who extracts the ^{131}I from the target. The solution already includes excipients, added to prevent the escape of significant amounts of dissolved volatile iodine [16]. In addition, these excipients are necessary to adjust the pH of the ^{131}I bulk solution, and to flavour the medicine for patients. For our application, the additional ingredients can indirectly affect the purity of the collected ^{131m}Xe , as detailed in Section 3.

Curium Pharma provides ^{131}I directly to hospitals and other partners (e.g. CERN) in a liquid NaI solution (shipped in a glass vial), or in the solid state (NaI powder in a gelatin capsule, to be swallowed by patients). Na^{131}I in the capsule format used in this work is prepared by adding a small volume of the solution to a NaI powder placed in a gelatin shell. Figure 2 shows one such capsule, and the powder, in scale.

2.3. Purchase of ^{131}I and radioactive decay

For every experiment, a single capsule containing Na^{131}I was delivered to CERN in a lead pot in a type-A package (Figure 2). The manufacturer specifies the activity to 10%, i.e. 50(5) MBq. Upon arrival, the actual ^{131}I activity in the capsule was determined with a calibrated High-Purity Germanium (HPGe) P-type extended range detector (model GX6020 by CANBERRA, Montigny-Le-Bretonneux, France), with a thin carbon window (Table 2). As an acquisition system, we used a multichannel analyzer model ASPEC-927

Figure 2. Standard elements of the transport packaging of the radiopharmaceutical ^{131}I . Left: type-A package. The lead container, held securely in polystyrene foam inside a cardboard box. Right, top: gelatin capsule and Na^{131}I powder.

and Maestro-32 software, both produced by ORTEC (AMETEK ORTEC, Oak Ridge, USA). Remote manipulators with machined grooves were used to open the gelatin shell, and to transport its content into a dedicated borosilicate glass tube. Figure 3 presents the tools used for the safe handling of the capsule. These were necessary to avoid exposure to a large radiation dose received directly to the operator's fingers. 117 118 119 120 121

Figure 3. I. Schematic of the opening setup. Operator (O) stands behind the protective panel and manipulates the source (S) with remote manipulators. The source is transferred to a glass tube that is then installed in the vacuum-tight experimental setup (labelled vacuum tube or VT in the schematic). II. Tools for safe handling of the source including: the acrylic remote manipulators with grooves machined to the size of the gelatin shell, the acrylic shielding panel (thickness 1 cm) stopping beta particles from the ^{131}I source, and the fast-drying glue necessary for the rapid attachment of the gelatin shell to the grooves in the acrylic manipulators. III. The acrylic support for the vacuum tube: a borosilicate glass annealing tube with a CF 16 flange. A glass funnel aids powder transfer and minimizes transfer losses.

Using the acrylic manipulators with a drop of fast drying glue *UHU Flextube Colle sans solvant* to attach the gelatin shell, the capsule was opened into two halves. With the acrylic manipulators, the Na^{131}I powder was then transferred from the gelatin capsule via a glass funnel into the borosilicate glass annealing tube (labelled VT or vacuum tube in Figure 3). γ -ray spectroscopy on the annealing vial (Figure 5) containing the powder provided a measurement of the activity of the transferred powder, and of the potential losses due to capsule manipulations (Table 2). Next, the tube was installed in the experimental setup for xenon production (Figure 4). 122 123 124 125 126 127 128 129

2.4. ^{131}I extraction and $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ collection

The setup for $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ collection (Figure 4) consisted of ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) elements (CF flanges, needle valves and gate valves). In addition, the setup contained the annealing tube with Na^{131}I and a collection vial for $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$, both made of borosilicate glass.

An UHV valve was mounted between the annealing tube and rest of the setup. The tip of the tube which contained the transferred Na^{131}I powder was inserted into a furnace equipped with temperature stability controls (measured temperature drift $\leq 2\text{ K}$). The Na^{131}I powder was heated to up to $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to allow for xenon to diffuse out of the powder. Each heating treatment lasted 1 hour, with increasing temperatures for consecutive treatments.

The collection vial was mounted vertically in the setup. The free space below it was used to place a container with liquid nitrogen—a cryotrap—for $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ collection. Collections were performed after every one-hour-long heat treatment.

Figure 4. Top: Schematic of the extraction setup. The Na^{131}I source (labelled 1), is in the glass annealing tube inside the furnace. The collection vial for $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ is labelled 2. Black rectangles denote valves dividing the installation into separate cells. Bottom: A photograph of the experimental installation for xenon extraction and collection.

The experimental setup was evacuated to 10^{-6} mbar with a turbomolecular pump, and an oil-free scroll pump. Two pressure gauges were integrated into the system to cover the pressure range from UHV to atmospheric pressure. A full-range vacuum gauge (labelled G1 in the bottom of Figure 4) housing two sensors—a Pirani gauge and a cold-cathode ionisation gauge—was installed between the pumping system and the chamber in contact with xenon. This location was optimal for a wide range of vacuum regimes, but it was not used in the presence of xenon, due to the ionic pumping effect. A capacitance diaphragm

vacuum gauge (labelled G2 in the bottom of Figure 4) was installed at the interface between the gas diffusing from the annealing vial and the collection vial. That gauge measured the direct force on the diaphragm, and could consequently measure the pressure independently of gas type and concentration. In addition, it did not pump xenon like an ionisation gauge would.

After each collection, the valve to the collection vial was closed and the cryotrap was removed to allow *in situ* γ -ray spectroscopy to characterize how collections depended on the temperature of the heating cycles. We used two γ -ray detectors. The first one was a 2x2 inch LaBr₃(Ce) crystal encapsulated in aluminium. Thin aluminium housing and a glass light guide allowed for acquisition of 29.8 keV X-rays from decay of ^{131m}Xe to the ground state (branching ratio 29.3%). The latter was an HPGe detector, model GC7020 from CANBERRA (Montigny-Le-Brettonneux, France), with an aluminum window blocking X-ray radiation (including at 29.3 keV), but sensitive to higher energy radiations (^{131m}Xe: 164 keV and ¹³¹I: 364 keV). We used the CAEN DT5730 (8 Channel 14 bit 500 MS/s Digitizer) with the PHA firmware and Compass software (<https://www.caen.it/products/dt5730/>) The distance between the center axis of the collection vial and the detectors was 55 mm and 80 mm, respectively, for the LaBr₃(Ce) and the HPGe detector. A 10-cm-thick lead shielding was placed between the Na¹³¹I source and the detectors to reduce the ¹³¹I background, and to prevent saturating the HPGe preamplifier due to high count rates from the iodine source. The Na¹³¹I source was at the distance of about 60 cm from the detectors.

After completion of the heat treatment cycles, the collection vial with xenon was detached from the experimental setup, and transported to a second γ -ray spectroscopy station (with CANBERRA detector model GX6020) for *a posteriori* determination of activity, without the ¹³¹I background (see Figure 6). A calibrated ¹⁵²Eu source was used for the energy calibration and to determine the detection efficiency at energies $E_\gamma < 1.5$ MeV, see Table 1 for efficiencies values listed for the sources of interest.

Table 1. Detection efficiencies of CANBERRA detector model GX6020 in γ -ray spectroscopy of Na¹³¹I powder and ^{131m}Xe collection vial.

Source	Distance source – detector d [cm]	Energy [keV]	Detection efficiency
^{131m} Xe	50	163.9	7.79(12)E-4
		364.5	4.98(15)E-4
Na ¹³¹ I	154	364.5	5.65(13)E-5

3. Results

3.1. Efficiency of ^{131m}Xe generator

Three types of γ -ray spectroscopy measurements were taken and used for the calculations shown in Table 2: activity of the Na¹³¹I capsule, activity of the Na¹³¹I powder transferred to the vial, and activity of the collected ^{131m}Xe. Example spectra are shown in Figures 5 (transferred ¹³¹I powder) and 6 (collected ^{131m}Xe). The Figures present the number of counts per channel (6 channels per 1 keV) as a function of the energy in keV. In Fig. 5 main gamma transitions for ¹³¹I are marked and labelled: 364.5 keV (branching ratio 81.5%), 637.0 keV (7.16%), 284.3 keV (6.12%), 80.2 keV (2.6%), and 722.9 keV (1.8%) [13]. The γ -ray decay branch—at 364.5 keV—was used for the determination of the ¹³¹I activity. The sample was also verified for presence of impurities (mostly ¹³³I and ¹³⁵I) and no impurities were found. For ^{131m}Xe activity determination in the spectra of collection vials, the γ -ray transition of 163.9 keV (1.95% branching) was used. The transition to the ground state proceeds mostly via emission of conversion electrons (29.8 keV (29.3%), 29.5 keV (15.8%), 33.6–34.5 keV (10.5%), 33.6–33.9 keV (8.5%)) [13]. Spectra of ^{131m}Xe were recorded in a low-background environment, free of a ¹³¹I source. This low background baseline allowed for a relatively precise determination of radionuclidic purity of ^{131m}Xe (see Table 3).

Figure 5. γ -ray spectroscopy of the ^{131}I powder after the transfer into the annealing vial, recorded in the ISOLDE experimental hall. The γ radiation characteristic of ^{131}I are labelled in black. These are lines at: 364.5 keV (81.5%), 637.0 keV (7.16%), 284.3 keV (6.12%), 80.2 keV (2.6%), and 722.9 keV (1.8%). The γ radiation of the background [17] is marked in grey in the plot.

Figure 6. γ -ray spectrum of the collected $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ sample, recorded in the ISOLDE experimental hall. The decay radiation characteristic of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ is labelled in black. The γ -ray transition is at 163.9 keV (1.95%). The X-rays are at: 29.8 keV (29.3%), 29.5 keV (15.8%), 33.6-34.5 keV (10.5%), 33.6-33.9 keV (8.5%). The main γ -ray peak of ^{131}I decay (364.5 keV) is labelled and marked in red. The γ radiation of the background [17] is marked in grey.

Table 2 summarizes the results of experiments with 3 batches of Na^{131}I and collected $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$. Column 2 is the measured activity of Na^{131}I capsule in MBq upon delivery of the sample to CERN-ISOLDE. The value for each experiment agrees with the procurement of 50(5) MBq. Column 3 is the time between the end of manufacturing (EOM) of the Na^{131}I capsule, reported by Curium Pharma, and the γ -ray spectroscopy of Na^{131}I capsule at CERN-ISOLDE. It allows to determine the initial capsule's activity. Column 4 (transfer rate ρ) is a percentage of delivered ^{131}I activity that got transferred to the annealing tube and it was calculated based on two γ -ray spectroscopy measurements: of ^{131}I capsule and of transferred ^{131}I powder. The value of ρ varies, as it depends on the Na^{131}I saturation of the

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NaI powder and gelatin shell with the ^{131}I bulk solution during the capsule's preparation process. For instance, for experiment ID 1, a significant percentage of ^{131}I (about 36%) was in the gelatin shell, which was cast aside.

Columns 5, 6 and 7 relate to $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ activity. Column 5 details the activity of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ expected at the end of collection (EOC) based on ^{131}I activity at EOM given $\alpha = 62\%$ and ρ . The value of α was determined based on $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ collection at room temperature. Column 6 presents the measured $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ activity at EOC. The measurements were taken without the iodine background, and after a complete cycle of heat treatments (see Figure 6). Column 7 specifies the collection efficiency as a ratio between measured $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ (Column 6) and the estimated $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ activity at EOC (Column 5). The collection efficiency was 85% on average.

Table 2. Efficiency of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ production and collection from decay of ^{131}I .

ID	Measured ^{131}I activity at delivery [MBq] *	Time between EOM and delivery [days]	^{131}I transfer rate ρ	Determined $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ activity at EOC (given ρ and α) [kBq]	Measured $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ activity at EOC [kBq] *	Efficiency of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ collection
1	49.0(5)	6	64(1) %	119(4)	99(2)	83(3) %
2	51.1(6)	2	85(2) %	149(5)	131(4)	88(3) %
3	47.5(4)	22	96(2) %	240(7)	204(1)	85(3) %

* — measured with CANBERRA detector model GX6020

EOM — end of manufacturing of ^{131}I capsule

EOC — end of collection of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$

ρ — the transfer rate of ^{131}I from the capsule to the vial

α — the release rate of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ at ambient conditions

3.2. Collection efficiency as a function of temperature

One of the objectives of this work was to establish the most suitable conditions to extract $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ from a Na^{131}I salt and, as a result, to minimize the workload and time needed to achieve the optimized collection. For this purpose the collection efficiency as a function of the heating temperature was studied. ^{131}I was heated up to 400 °C in several steps.

Figure 7 summarizes all collections of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ taken after heating cycles to given temperatures. The Y-axis presents percentages of the total collected activity of $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ as a function of extraction temperature. Samples 1 and 2 were heated multiple times to temperatures between 40 °C and 100 °C over a course of 14 days, and their percentages of total activity are the sums of activities from all collections at a given temperature. For sample 3, the experiment's protocol was improved and all collections were executed successively on day 14 with each temperature threshold reached only once.

For practical reasons, the sample was not replaced between the heating cycles at different temperatures. Therefore, the thermal diffusion coefficient could not be derived. However, the collected data allowed to establish that the temperature threshold stimulating $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ diffusion out of Na^{131}I powder is below or at room temperature. For heat treatments up to 100 °C: 84%, 64%, and 99% of all collected $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ was measured for samples 1 to 3, respectively. In addition, in the first collection—at room temperature—for sample 3, 69% of total collected $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ activity was measured. In summary, for a time-saving $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ collection operation with relatively minimal losses it would be sufficient to heat the Na^{131}I sample to 200 °C.

3.3. Radionuclidic purity of generated $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$

MDA is the minimum detectable activity, here expressed in Bq, at a specified confidence level. It is usually calculated at the 95% confidence level, which means there's a 95% certainty that the activity above MDA threshold would be detected. For future clinical applications, it is important to establish MDA of ^{131}I in every end-product $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ vial.

Figure 7. Percentage of ^{131m}Xe activity collected at the temperature T normalized to the total collected ^{131m}Xe activity.

Table 3 presents, for each of the 3 experiments (column 1: ID): the minimum detectable activity (MDA) of ^{131}I (Column 2), the ^{131}I activity determined from the area under the peak at 364.5 keV (Column 3), the detected presence or absence of radiation from ^{131}I in the spectrum (Column 4) based on the comparison of Columns 2 and 3, and the ratio of ^{131}I residual activity to ^{131m}Xe activity, expressed in % (Column 5). Calculations of MDA are based on Currie's derivation for single measurements [18]. With 95% level of confidence, the simplified formula reads as follows [19]:

$$MDA = \frac{2.71 + 4.66 \sigma}{t \cdot d_{eff} \cdot y} \quad (2)$$

where: $2.71 = k_1^2$, $4.66 = 2\sqrt{2}k_1$, k_1 is the one-sided confidence factor = 1.645 at 95% confidence, t is the time of acquisition, σ is the standard deviation of the background collected at time t , d_{eff} is the detection efficiency for the γ -ray peak at 364 keV, and y is the branching ratio for the emission of γ -ray peak at 364 keV.

Table 3. Minimum detectable activity of ^{131}I in the ^{131m}Xe collection sample.

ID	MDA [Bq]	Determined ^{131}I activity [Bq]	Radiation from ^{131}I	Ratio $^{131}\text{I} : ^{131m}\text{Xe}$
1	28.6	186(50)	Present	0.2%
2	4.1	37(13)	Present	0.03%
3	7.4	56(9)	Present	0.03%

As shown in the table, for all experiments the counts in the peak area at 364.5 keV were above the MDA limit. Thus, with confidence at the level of 95% ^{131}I was present in ^{131m}Xe sample and equal 186(50) Bq, 37(13) Bq and 56(9) Bq, for ID 1, 2 and, 3 respectively. The ratio of ^{131}I activity to ^{131m}Xe activity for three experiments was: 0.19%, 0.03%, and

0.03%. The elevated ratio for the first experiment might come from the residual activity of iodine that remained in the setup from an earlier series of the experiments.

4. Discussion

The purpose of this research was to study the generation of the long-lived excited state ^{131m}Xe by thermal sublimation, from the decay of a commercially obtained ^{131}I solid-state source.

γ -ray spectroscopy showed that with consecutive heat treatments between 40 °C and 400 °C, up to 88% of the estimated produced ^{131m}Xe can be routinely collected. The remaining ^{131m}Xe is possibly trapped in the Na^{131}I powder, which starts to sinter at 200 °C. This hypothesis could not be verified with γ -ray spectroscopy because of high signal of the Na^{131}I background. In addition, up to 69% of the total ^{131m}Xe can be already collected at room temperature.

^{131}I decays only to the metastable ^{131m}Xe and to the ground state ^{131}Xe . It represents therefore a possible production route of high radionuclidic purity available throughout the year, unlike production routes that necessitate a radioactive ion beam facility, or a reactor. The activity of ^{131}I was found in the end-product collection vial at the level of 0.03% in two experiments, while it was at the level of 0.2% in the first experiment, possibly from a residual presence of iodine in the setup predating this series of experiments. However, certain limitations of the detailed method have to be considered. First, the activity of ^{131m}Xe is about 300 times smaller than that of the ^{131}I generator given lossless transfer of Na^{131}I powder to the experimental setup. Moreover, despite high radionuclidic purity, products of thermal decomposition of stable excipients are present in the end-product collection vial. These include oxides of: carbon, phosphorus, and sulphur. Thus, purification methods of the end product would have to be implemented prior to deployment for the GAMMA-MRI project. Moreover, collection of ^{131m}Xe would have to be planned 13 to 15 days in advance of a subsequent experiment to allow for ^{131}I decay and production of sufficient amounts of ^{131m}Xe . Thus, an experimental setup needs to be dedicated solely to this goal for a whole period of approximately two weeks.

5. Conclusions and outlook

An affordable and accessible production method of long-lived ^{131m}Xe isomer via radioactive decay of commercially available ^{131}I was investigated. Our thermal sublimation generator is dedicated to supplying the long-lived ^{131m}Xe for optimization tests of laser polarization in the GAMMA-MRI project. If the production of ^{131m}Xe was to be up-scaled and appropriate chemical purification implemented, this technique could be deployed to the production of moderate quantities of ^{131m}Xe suited for small scale experiments such as GAMMA-MRI.

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